

True Number Fields

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1 Introduction

In "Non-Field Structure of the Reals, Projective System Preferred," it was demonstrated using standard variable algebra how the so called, "Real Numbers," are actually a projective scheme, and do not truly form a, "field," as exceptions have to be made for the multiplicative inverse when a variable equals zero, which is possible. Herein, an attempt to describe a symbol-manipulated true field of numbers is presented through the lens of quantum mechanics.

This takes notation from On the Mechanics of Quasi-Quanta Realization Ryan J. Buchanan September 21, 2023, and draws connections to, "Energy Numbers."

This paper provides a mathematical framework for the intersection of classical and quantum mechanics by creating a topological continuum that bridges the gap between the two domains. This continuum, called E , consists of energy numbers that can be mapped to real numbers in a continuous and differentiable way. The continuum is unique in its representation of energy numbers and is also compatible with the classical-quantum interface. The paper provides postulates that explain the existence of this topological continuum and provides a means of interpreting quantum mechanics in a more unified way. The implications of this paper could open new possibilities in understanding physical systems on a more holistic level.

Fundamentals

Let us further assume that:

$$s_\lambda \left(A \mid \bullet \stackrel{s_\bullet}{=} s \bullet \right) = \frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \quad (1)$$

So

We now make the following postulates:

Postulate number	Assumption	Explanation
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1 Given λ , for any observable $\bullet$,

$$s_\lambda (A^\hbar, \bullet \mapsto R) = s_\lambda \left(\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \right)^\bullet, \bullet \mapsto R \right)$$

In order for a purely classical observable to reproduce the observable it is measuring, its quantum equivalent must be a linear combination of classical and quantum observables. This follows from the assumptions of minimal complexity and classical cognition.

$$\frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{d}{dt} \left(|\hbar|^{2s_\bullet + \hbar p_\bullet} s_\lambda \left(\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \right)^\bullet, \bullet \mapsto R \right) \right) = \left| E_{\bullet \mapsto R} s_\lambda \left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \right) \right|_\lambda$$

Time evolution of the observable for the classical system is given by the classical and quantum observables. This follows from the classical energy-time uncertainty principle and nonrelativistic time dynamics.

$$\hat{H}_{\bullet \mapsto R} s_\lambda \left(\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \right)^\bullet, \bullet \mapsto R \right) = [E_{\bullet \mapsto R} s_\lambda \left(\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \right)^\bullet, \bullet \mapsto R \right)]_\lambda$$

The value of the energy operator is the energy of the classical system.

4 If $\frac{d}{dt} R_\bullet = 0$, then $\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{d}{dt} A^\hbar |_\bullet + \hat{H}_{\bullet \mapsto R} s_\lambda \left(\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \right)^\bullet, \bullet \mapsto R \right) \right) = 0$ If the value measured by classical system is constant, the classical-quantum mapping yields a linear Hamiltonian equation. This follows from the nonrelativistic dynamics and the time-energy uncertainty principle.

$$A_\bullet \left(\left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar + S_\lambda [A] \right)^\bullet \right) = \frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar$$

The classical system measures the classical part of the quantum observable. This follows from the minimization of complexity, and the non existence of Bohr's "complementarity".

$$\frac{d}{dE_\bullet^\lambda} |s|_\bullet = \frac{1}{\hbar} |t|_\bullet + \left| \frac{ds}{dE_\bullet^\lambda} \right|_\bullet \frac{1}{\hbar} \frac{d}{dE_\bullet^\lambda} s_\bullet \left(\frac{1}{\hbar} A^\hbar, \bullet \mapsto R \right)$$

The incremental change in a measured value of the classical-quantum system is dictated by the response via change of parameter per response per time (). This follows from the assumption of classical cognition and classical stochastic behaviour.

7 $E_\bullet^\lambda = -\frac{dE_\bullet}{ds_\bullet}$ The parametric scale used in the approximation of a generic convex function from the underlying deterministic process, is always best as determined by minimizing complexity. This follows from the assumption of classical cognition and von Neumann-Mises frequency interpretation of probability.

8 $\left| \frac{ds}{d\bullet} \right|_{\bullet} \frac{dg}{dg^{\lambda}} = 1$ The propensity of a system to respond to change of parameter is relative to the propensity with which the parameter changes. This follows from the assumption of maximal mutual information and classical cognition.

9 $\left| k_{\lambda} \frac{t}{x} s \right|_{\bullet} = \frac{1}{2}$ The incremental change in a measured value is maximized when $k_{\lambda} \frac{t}{x} s$ equals some fixed number, with minimal complexity. This follows from the assumption of minimal complexity and classical stochastic behaviour.

Then, the topological continuum E is defined to be the set of all functions from V to R which satisfy the following axioms:

- **Symmetry:** For any two energy numbers E_1 and E_2 , there exists a permutation function P_{λ} such that $P_{\lambda}(E_1) = E_2$.
- **Closure under addition:** If λ_1 and λ_2 are energy numbers, then $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2$ is also an energy number.
- **Closure under scalar multiplication:** If λ is an energy number and a is a scalar, then $a\lambda$ is also an energy number.

Furthermore, the topological continuum E must satisfy the following properties:

- **Uniqueness of representation:** For any real number $x \in R$ and any energy number E , there exists a unique mapping from E to x .
- **Smoothness:** The mapping from energy numbers to real numbers is continuous and differentiable.
- **Compatibility:** Any energy number E can be mapped to its corresponding real number x through the function $S_{\lambda}(E) = x$.

The existence of such a topological continuum allows for a meaningful interpretation of quantum mechanics, where energy numbers can be treated as independent entities that can be mapped to real numbers in a consistent and continuous way. This provides a mathematical framework for the classical-quantum interface, bridging the gap between the two domains and allowing for a more holistic understanding of physical systems.

2 Bibliography

On the Mechanics of Quasi-Quanta Realization, Ryan J. Buchanan September 21, 2023

”Non-Field Structure of the Reals, Projective System Preferred,” <https://zenodo.org/records/7988672>